

SUPPORTING 'LEARNING BY DOING' PHILOSOPHY THROUGH A NEW COURSE

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Annotation: The article deals with the theme supporting learning by doing philosophy through a new course. Moreover, the theory of learning by doing in methodology were discussed.

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In fact, there are a number of different approaches or terms within this broad heading, such as experiential learning, co-operative learning, adventure learning and apprenticeship. I will use the term 'experiential learning' as a broad umbrella term to cover this wide variety of approaches to learning by doing. There are many different theorists in this area, such as John Dewey (1938) and more recently David Kolb (1984). Simon Fraser University defines experiential learning as:

“the strategic, active engagement of students in opportunities to learn through doing, and reflection on those activities, which empowers them to apply their theoretical knowledge to practical endeavours in a multitude of settings inside and outside of the classroom.”

There is a wide range of design models that aim to embed learning within real world contexts, including:

- ✓ laboratory, workshop or studio work;
- ✓ apprenticeship;
- ✓ problem-based learning;
- ✓ case-based learning;
- ✓ project-based learning;
- ✓ inquiry-based learning;
- ✓ cooperative (work- or community-based) learning.

The focus here is on some of the main ways in which experiential learning can be designed and delivered, with particular respect to the use of technology, and in ways that help develop the knowledge and skills needed in a digital age[1]. Learning by doing is a growing methodology due to its advantages in learning. It seeks to acquire knowledge while developing skills and abilities to solve real problems that students may encounter throughout their life and professional experience.

Proponents of this methodology argue that discussions, practice, and teaching or exposing to others what you know are active methods with a higher rate of knowledge assimilation. Learning by doing is an active learning methodology based on experience to assimilate concepts through actions. It also encourages the student to learn from mistakes and draw conclusions after analyzing the practice in a clear spirit of continuous improvement. This is not a new concept, especially if we remember that Aristotle, as early as the 4th century BC, stated that “what we have to learn, we learn by doing.” However, some theorists point to the late 19th century American pedagogue John Dewey as the father of renewed education based on the method that concerns us in this article. Dewey considered that education should be active. The objective of learning by doing essentially seeks to prevent the student from forgetting the knowledge learned over time through experience instead of passively assimilating concepts through memory, making them much briefer.

The introduction of the “learning-by-doing” methodology in companies is also helping to improve employee commitment and performance. This is because people acquire knowledge and, at the same time, develop skills that they can transfer to other situations or colleagues[2]. “Learning by doing” is a pedagogical method based on the idea that you can learn something better and faster if you practice it – if you “do it”, as the name suggests. The method, theorized by the American philosopher, psychologist, and educational reformer John Dewey, seems quite straight forward. Learning by doing is a theory that places heavy emphasis on student engagement and is a hands-on, task-oriented, process to education. The theory refers to the process in which students actively participate in more practical and imaginative ways of learning. This process distinguishes itself from other learning approaches as it provides many pedagogical advantages to more traditional learning styles, such those which privilege inert knowledge. Learning-by-doing is related to other types of learning such as adventure learning, action learning, cooperative learning, experiential learning, peer learning, service-learning, and situated learning.

Much of what is known about the learning by doing theory was thanks to the contributions of historic minds that changed education today. The theory has been expounded and popularized by famous American philosopher and educational crusader John Dewey and Brazilian pedagogy Paulo Freire. Dewey, considered as one of the founding fathers of modern-day functional psychology, implemented this idea by setting up the University of Chicago Laboratory School. His views have been important in establishing practices of progressive education. He was an advocate for progressive education as opposed to traditional education. Dewey believed that effective learning is done through interactions and that school is a social institution where these interactions take place. In an ideal classroom in which learning by doing is implemented, the classroom is a space for children to learn and problem solve as a community in their own way, at their own pace,

through teacher instructions that take the children into consideration. This fosters a healthy and responsive learning community where students actively engage in the learning process. Learning by doing not only focuses on academic growth, but social, intellectual, emotional, physical, and spiritual growth.

Freire on the other hand, highlighted the important role of the individual development seeking to generate awareness and nurture critical skills based on his most influential pieces known as Pedagogy of the Oppressed. Dewey advocated for education as a means of preserving democracy and sound government because he was raised in advanced and civilized New York City. While in Brazil during the dictatorship, Freire experienced crushing poverty and a wretched lifestyle. Therefore, he advocated for education as a means of awareness and liberation from the problems associated with underdevelopment. Thus resulting these experiences to be the contributing factor to how he would construct his ideas on education.

Besides Freire and Dewey there were other key contributors to the learn-by-doing theory including Richard DuFour, who adopted and applied it to the development of professional learning communities. Richard DuFour was an education consultant and author who wanted to improve the education system in America. He was a leading voice in the movement to improve schools through professional learning communities, in which teachers come together to analyze and improve their classroom practice.

Despite being born blind it did not stop Jeremy Bruner from becoming successful, as he was able to get a Phd in psychology and taught in Harvard, Oxford and NY University[3]. Bruner was always focused on the American educational system and finding ways to improve it. He introduced the concepts of discovery learning and spiral curriculum. Discovery learning is depicted as a way for students to learn the given curriculum on their own accord and built upon it with their experiences. Spiral learning was Bruner's idea that similar topics can be

taught to any age, but according to the stage of thought.

David Kolb drew inspiration from Kurt Lewin, John Dewey, and Jean Piaget to create an experiential learning model[4]. Kolb believed that effective learners need to have concrete experience abilities (CE), reflective observation abilities (RO), abstract conceptualization (AC), and active experimentation (AE) abilities. Concrete experience is being involved and actively engaged in new experiences. Reflective observation is asking questions and discussing the experience. Abstract conceptualization is when the learner thinks and starts to make conclusions. Active experimentation is reapplying their conclusions to the task at hand to make decisions and solve problems.

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